

DETERMINING THE TEACHERS' LEVEL OF OBEYING THE ETHICAL RULES ACCORDING TO STUDENT PERCEPTION

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Abstract:

On this research, it is aimed to determine the teachers' level of obeying the ethical rules and find out about the relationship between instructors' ethical values and various variables. Research, in which scanning method is used, is performed with 182 learners on 2015-2016 educational year. For data collection, "*Teacher Ethical Value Scale according to Students Perception*", which is developed and tested for reliability by Gunduz and Coskun (2012). On statistical evaluation of gathered values, independent t-test, Mann Whitney u test and correlation matrix is used. On the other hand, values are evaluated on 0.01 and 0.05 meaningfulness level and their percentage, frequency, average and standard deviation values are also analysed. On the research, it is determined that class level and school type variables are effective ones on teachers' ethical standard of judgement. Yet, it is seen that there is no meaningful difference on gender variable.

Keywords: Ethics, ethical values, ethical values of teacher occupation, professional responsibility, professional sufficiency

1. Introduction

Introduction of concepts like ethics, ethical codes, ethical values and occupational ethics to human life had a significant effect on the evaluation and acceptance of performed behaviours. Ethics concept is described as "*all attitudes that should be obeyed or avoided among different occupation branches*". (TDK, 2013) When literature is analysed, there are also descriptions of ethics concepts that are created on different time periods. According to Moss Curtis (2006), ethics is through some detailed concepts like "*reality, justice,*

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honesty, trueness”, principles that lead the trueness or errors of behaviours and decisions”. According to another description, ethics is the moral principles and value system that leads to good-bad, correct-incorrect related with human behaviours. (Hatcher, 2004) Ethics is about how the evaluation criteria and criteria’s for individual behaviour, attitude and values in terms of society came into existence. (Karslı, 2004) Actually, when ethics is analysed, it is seen that it is a basic concept that has got a bound with all disciplines. On recent years, one of the significant areas that is held is occupational ethics. Occupational ethic is a concept that is mostly established on sociological basics. (Ozmen & Gungor, 2008) Occupational ethics can be described as behaviour rules that should be obeyed on occupations that have got a relation with human beings directly. (Aydin, 2003) As another expression, it is the rule combination that applies some rules about human beings’ being motivated to the good and true, limiting personal desires in occupation, improves occupational ideals and excludes unprincipled members from the occupation. (Aydin, 2015: p:55) Today, in all the world, the aim is to increase the quality of occupational members and the product that will come out as the result of performing the occupation, and hindering non-ethical behaviours. On this point, for raising individuals with ethical values, education institutions and learners have got huge responsibilities. (Kaya, 2015)

Since each profession has professional ethical principles (Pelit & Güçer, 2006), which has its own specific qualities and characteristics, ethics is also important in teaching profession. According to Erdem and Simsek (2013), ethics for teaching occupation is rules and principles that teachers should fulfil in relation to society, students and colleagues. Being a teacher is consisted of professional ethical principles like professionalism, responsibility on service, justice, equality, providing healthy and secure atmosphere, not having corruption and improving by being bound to the occupation. Students, who are aware of ethical values, will have what is right and good as a guide in their future profession (Karataş, 2013). Teachers, (Yaman, Çetinkaya Marble & Mutlugil, 2009), who will be aware of the rights and responsibilities of the pupils and will make learners to internalize them, have to adopt the professional ethics principles of teaching. On this point, how much do the teachers internalize “*teaching profession ethical principles and values*” becomes a significant research subject. It is because the values those individuals have got an effect on mainly to their profession, attitude, behaviour and decisions.

When literature about the subject is analysed, it can be seen that there are some studies related with ethics and occupational ethic. For example, studies that analyse the level of teachers and teacher candidates’ Professional ethic behaviours and their obeying ethical principles are (Gözütok, 1999; Karataş, 2013; Pelit & Güçer, 2006; Yılmaz

& Altunkurt, 2009; Öztürk, 2010). Karakaya and Arslan (2016) researched the ethical approaches about middle school 9th grade learners using animals on experiments. They found out that according various variables, ethical preferences changes.

In fact, students are the ones who will best assess teachers' compliance with ethical values. It is determined that the studies about teachers' obeying ethical values in terms of student perception are not efficient enough. (Tunca, Alkın-Şahin, Sever & Aktaş, 2015; Yeşilyurt & Kılıç, 2014; Arğa, 2012; Çelebi & Akbağ, 2012; Gündüz & Coşkun, 2011; Özen-Kutaniş, Bayraktaroğlu & Özdemir, 2005; Örenel, 2005). In addition, it has been observed that studies do not reveal the relationship between professional competence and professional responsibility. Because of these reasons, it is thought that this research will have a significant contribution to literature.

1.1 Aim of the Study

In this study, it was aimed to determine the level of teachers' compliance with ethical values and the relation of their ethical values with various variables according to their perceptions. Within the scope of this aim, the following research questions were searched:

- Do the ethical values of the teachers differ according to the students' gender according to student perception?
- Do the ethical values of the teachers differ according to the students' school type?
- Do the ethical values that teachers have according to student perception differ according to the class level of the students?
- What are the level, direction and level of significance of the relationship between the variables of professional responsibility and vocational competence?

2. Method

In this research, scanning design was used from quantitative research methods. Scanning Descriptive is a numerical description of the attitude, tendencies, or opinions of the universe as a result of analysis on the sample selected from the researcher's universe (Bursal, 2014, 155).

2.1 Data Collection Tool

"*Teacher Ethical Values Scale According to Student Perception*", which is constructed by the researchers and (2) experts 'opinion is obtained for and '*Personal Information Questionnaire*', which is developed by Gündüz and Coşkun (2012) are used for

gathering students' demographical information. Options and points in positive expressions in the scale, which is prepared according to the Adjective List; 5 = Many (4.21-5.00), 4 = Very (3.41-4.20), 3 = Medium (2.61-3.40), 2 = Less than (1.81-2.60) and 1 = Never (1.00-1.80).

The scale consists totally 30 items, the first dimension as "*Professional Responsibility (19)*" and the second dimension as "*Vocational Qualification (11)*". Gündüz and Coşkun (2012) determined the Cronbach's alpha value of the professional responsibility dimension as .94, the vocational qualification dimension as .86 and the overall scale as Cronbach's alpha as .95. In this study, the occupational responsibility dimension is .92, the vocational qualification dimension is .80, and the overall scale's Cronbach's alpha is .94. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient (.94) obtained as a result of the research showed that the reliability of the scale is high.

2.2 Data Analysis

The data obtained from students in secondary level (4th, 5th, 6th, 7th. and 8th grade) is analysed with the aid of the IBM SPSS 21 statistical program. Independent-t test, Mann-Whitney u test and correlation matrix are used to evaluate the data obtained from the study. In addition, percentages, frequencies, average and standard deviation values are given in the study by an evaluation on the meaning level of 0.01 and 0.05.

2.3 Research Group

The universe of the research is consisted of 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grade students from Kahramanmaraş province. The study group of the study consisted of 182 individuals selected by appropriate sampling method. The distribution of the demographic characteristics of the students participating in the survey is given on Table 1.

Table 1: Students' demographical characteristics

		f	%
Gender	Female	88	48.4
	Male	94	51.6
Grade	4 th and 5 th	57	31.3
	6 th ,7 th and 8 th	125	68.7
School Type	Government	96	52.7
	Private	86	47.3
Total		182	100

When the data in Table 1 is examined, 31.3% (n = 57) of the samples are from 4th and 5th class, 68.7% (n = 125) are from 6th, 7th and 8th grade student. 48.4% (n = 88) of these students are female and 51.6% (n = 94) are male.

3. Findings

In this section, the obtained data in which the ethical values of the teachers are analysed in terms of various variables according to the perception of middle school second level students is presented. The minimum, maximum, average and standard deviation values of the scale and sub-dimensions used in the study are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Values related to teachers' ethical values scale and sub-dimensions according to student's perception

Test Sub Dimensions	N	Min	Max	$\bar{X}$	SD
Professional Responsibility (PR)	182	1.53	5.00	3.82	0.79
Professional Sufficiency (PS)		2.45	5.00	4.14	0.66
Scale	182	1.93	5.00	3.94	0.72

When the data in Table 2 is examined, it is determined that teachers' ethical values in the dimension of professional competence ($\bar{x} = 4.14$) is higher according to student perception. In this study, the effects of gender, school type, mother education level, father education level, level of class on teacher ethics according to student perception were investigated.

Firstly on research, an answer to the question “Do the ethical values of the teachers differ according to the gender of the students according to student perception?” is searched and gathered independent t-test results are given on Table 3.

Table 3: T test analysis results according to gender

Test Sub Dimension	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	sd	t	p
Professional Responsibility (PR)	Female	88	3.88	180	-.884	0.378
	Male	94	3.77			
Professional Sufficiency (PS)	Female	88	4.24	180	-1.942	0.54
	Male	94	4.05			
Scale	Female	88	4.01	180	-1.266	0.207
	Male	94	3.87			

*p<0.05

When data from Table 3 is analysed, it is determined that there is no meaningful difference according to gender variable on teachers' points ($t(180) = -1.266$; $p > 0.05$) that they gathered from teacher ethical values scale according to students' perception.

On the study, an answer to question “Do the ethical values of the teachers differ according to the students’ school type?” is searched and gathered independent t-test results are given on Table 4.

Table 4: Independent t-test results according to school type

Test Sub Dimensions	School type	N	$\bar{X}$	sd	t	p
Professional Responsibility (PR)	Government	96	4.05	180	4.19	0.00*
	Private	86	3.57			
Professional Sufficiency (PS)	Government	96	4.39	180	5.74	0.00*
	Private	86	3.87			
Scale	Government	96	4.17	180	4.85	0.00*
	Private	86	3.68			

*p<0.05

When data on Table 4 is analysed, it is seen that there is a meaningful difference on teacher points ($t(180) = 4.85$; $p < 0.05$) from teacher ethical values scale according to student perception related with the school type. On the other hand, according to student perception, meaningfulness is determined on teachers’ Professional responsibility ($t(180) = 4.19$; $p < 0.05$) and Professional sufficiency ($t(180) = 5.74$; $p < 0.05$). The result is gathered about government student learners are obeying ethical values more than the ones in private school.

On research, an answer to question “According to student perception, do the ethical values of the teachers differ according to the class level of the students?” is searched and gathered Mann-Whitney U test results are presented on Table 5.

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U test analysis results according to grade level

Scale	Grade level	N	Line Avg.	U	p
Professional Responsibility (PR)	4 th and 5 th	57	126.53	1566	.000*
	6 th , 7 th and 8 th	125	75.53		
Professional Sufficiency (PS)	4. ve 5. grade	57	121.91	1829	.000*
	6 th , 7 th and 8 th	125	77.63		
Scale	4 th and 5 th	57	126.11	1590	.000*
	6 th , 7 th and 8 th	125	75.22		

*p<0.05

When the data in Table 5 were examined, it was found that there was a meaningful ($U = 1590$, $p < 0.05$).difference according to the students' perceptions according to the ethical values scale. On the other hand, it is seen that there is a meaningful difference on Professional responsibility ($U=1566$; $p < 0.05$) and Professional sufficiency ($U=1829$; $p < 0.05$) ethical values according to students’ perceptions. It is determined that 4th and

5th grade learners have got a better perception of teacher ethical values than 6th, 7th and 8th grade.

An answer to question “*What is the level, direction and level of significance of the relationship between the variables of professional responsibility and vocational competence?*” is searched and gathered correlation matrix is provided on Table 6.

Table 6: Correlation matrix results between professional responsibility and professional sufficiency

Correlation Matrix	Professional responsibility	Professional sufficiency
Professional Responsibility (PR)	r	.858**
	p	.000
Professional Sufficiency (PS)	r	.858**
	p	.000

p<0.01** r: Correlation level p: Meaningfulness Level

When the data in Table 5 are examined, there is a high level and meaningful relationship between teachers' professional responsibility and professional competence variables ($r = .858$ $p < 0.01$) in the positive direction according to the perceptions of the students.

4. Discussion and Results

In this study, it was aimed to determine the level of teachers' compliance with ethical values and the relation of their ethical values with various variables according to the perception of middle school students. According to the perceptions of the students, the level of compliance of the teachers with ethical values is high ($x = 3.94$). In addition, it is seen that teachers are competent with their professional responsibilities and sufficiency 'is 'very' much. These results are showing parallelism with researches by Tunca and et al. (2015); Yeşilyurt and Kılıç (2014); Gündüz and Coşkun (2011); Örenel (2005). The high level of compliance with ethical values of teachers who have great responsibility in education and training is an important result both for the students and for the education of the country.

In the study, it was determined that there was no statistical difference ($p > 0.05$) in the ethical values of the teachers according to the perception of male and female students. However, it was concluded that female students perceived that their teachers were more satisfied with ethical values than male students. The different ethical behaviours that women and men show against the events they have experienced can be effective in bringing about this outcome (Özen-Kutunis, Bayraktaroğlu & Özdemir,

2005). This result is parallel with results by Tunca and et al. (2015); Yeşilyurt and Kılıç (2014); Çelebi and Akbağ (2012); Gündüz and Coşkun (2011); Uğurlu (2008) from literature.

The research showed that the students had a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the ethical values that the teachers had according to the student perception of the school classroom. According to the perception of the students who attended public school, it was determined that teachers had higher scores on occupational responsibility, vocational competence and overall scale.

The study showed that the statistical difference ($p < 0.05$) in the ethical values teachers had in class level according to student perception. The developmental periods in which individuals are present influence their relationships and expectations with the people around them (Tunca et al., 2015). Individuals who are trained in the fourth and fifth grades have the conception of self-acceptance and acceptance (Tunca et al., 2015). The students who are studying in the upper classes are looking at the behaviours of the people who are in their surroundings and the characteristics of their adolescence with a critical eye (Can, 2013). This information reveals the statistical significance of the class level variable obtained from the research in the ethical values that the teachers have according to student perception. This result coincides with the results of Tunca et al (2015), Gündüz and Coşkun (2011); Örenel (2005) studies in the literature. According to student perception in the research, it was determined that the teachers had a high level of positive meaningfulness between the professional responsibility and professional competence variables. This result overlaps with the findings of the research that Yeşilyurt and Kılıç (2014) made.

As a result, it is necessary for the teachers who carry out the profession of teaching profession to adopt professional ethical values. It is important that professional competence and professional responsibilities are always a principle to instructors. In these in-service trainings, these principles should be kept and developed on the frontline. It is predicted that researches can be done according to different parameters by student perceptions in future researches.

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References

1. Arğa, M. (2012). *Öğretmenlerin mesleki etik ilkeleri kapsamındaki davranışlarının ilkokul ve ortaokul öğrencilerinin algularıyla değerlendirilmesi*. (Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). Yeditepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
2. Aydın, İ. (2015). *Eğitim ve öğretimde etik*. Ankara: Pegem A Yayınevi (7.baskı).
3. Aydın, İ. (2003). *Eğitim ve öğretimde etik*, Ankara, Pegem Yayıncılık.
4. Aydoğan, İ. (2011). Öğretmenlerin mesleki etik ilkelere uyma düzeylerinin öğrenciler tarafından algılanması. *Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 21(2), 87-96.
5. Bursal, M. (2014). Nicel Yöntemler. Selçuk Beşir Demir (Ed.) *Nitel, Nicel ve Karma Yöntem Yaklaşımları* (s:155-182). Ankara: Eğiten Kitap.
6. Can, G. (2013). *Kişilik gelişimi psikososyal ve ahlak gelişimi*. (Edt. B. Yeşilyaprak). Eğitim Psikolojisi. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
7. Çelebi, N., & Akbağ, M. (2012). Genel liselerde çalışan öğretmenlerin etik davranışlarını belirlemeye yönelik bir araştırma, *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(2), 425-441.
8. Erdem, A. R., & Şimşek, S. (2013). Öğretmenlik meslek etiğinin irdelenmesi. *Adıyaman Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 6(15), 185-203.
9. Gözütok, F. D. (1999). Öğretmen adaylarının etik davranışları, *Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32(1-2), 83-99.
10. Gündüz, Y., & Coşkun, Z. S. (2012). Öğrenci algısına göre öğretmen etik değerler ölçeğinin geliştirilmesi: Geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Kırşehir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 13(1), 111-131.
11. Gündüz, Y., & Coşkun, Z. S. (2011). İlköğretim öğrencilerinin öğretmenlerinin mesleki etik ilkelere uyma düzeyine ilişkin görüşleri, *Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 11(2), 95-110.

12. Hatcher, T. (2004) Environmental ethics as an alternative for evaluation theory in for-profit business contexts. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 27, 357-363
13. Karakaya, F., & Arslan, O. (2016). Öğrencilerin hayvan deneylerine yönelik etik yaklaşımları: 9.sınıf örneği. *Turkish Journal of Education*, 5(4), 208-223. Doi:10.19128/turje.267916
14. Karataş, A. (2013). İlköğretim öğretmen adayları için meslek etiğinin önemi, *Marmara Coğrafya Dergisi*, (28), 304-318.
15. Karslı, M. D. (2004). *Yönetmelik etkililik*. Ankara: Pegem A Yayıncılık.
16. Kaya, İ., (2015). Etik değerlere yatkınlık ölçeği geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Uluslararası Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 8(41), 968-974.
17. Moss Curtis, D. (2006). Everything I wanted to know about teaching law school, I learned from being a kindergarten teacher: Ethics in the law school classroom. *B.Y.U. Education and Law Journal*, 455-498
18. Örenel, S. (2005). *Öğretmenlerin mesleki etik ilkeleri kapsamındaki davranışlarının ilköğretim ve ortaöğretim öğrencilerinin algılarıyla değerlendirilmesi*. (Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). Marmara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü. İstanbul.
19. Özen-Kutunis, R., Bayraktaroğlu, S., & Özdemir, Y. (Kasım, 2005). Etik davranışların yöneliminde cinsiyet faktörü: Bir devlet üniversitesi örneği. II. Siyasette ve Yönetimde Etik Sempozyumu. (ss. 211-218). Sakarya: Sakarya Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi.
20. Özmen, F., & Güngör, A. (2008). Eğitim Denetiminde Etik. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9(15), 137-155.
21. Pelit E., & Güçer, E. (2006). Ticaret ve turizm meslek dersi öğretmen adaylarının öğretmenlik mesleği ile ilgili etik olmayan davranışlara ve öğretmenleri etik dışı davranışlara yönelten faktörlere ilişkin algılamaları, *Gazi Üniversitesi Ticaret ve Turizm Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* (2), 95-119.
22. TDK.(2013).*Etik*,http://www.tdk.gov.tr/index.php?option=com_gts&arama=gts&guid=TDK.GTS.582ee6c888ee40.85038142, Erişim Tarihi: 18.11.2016.
23. Tunca, N., Alkın-Şahin, S., Sever, D., & Aktaş, B. Ç. (2015). Teachers' level of compliance to ethical values based on secondary students' perceptions/Ortaokul öğrencilerinin algılarına göre öğretmenlerin etik değerlere uyma düzeyleri. *Eğitimde Kuram ve Uygulama*, 11(2), 398-419.
24. Yeşilyurt, E., & Kılıç, M. (2014). Ortaokul öğrencilerinin algılarına göre öğretmenlerin etik değerlere uyma düzeylerinin değerlendirilmesi. *EKEV Akademi Dergisi*, 18(60), 471-486.
25. Yılmaz, K., & Altunkurt, Y. (2009). Öğretmen adaylarının mesleki etik dışı davranışlar ile ilgili görüşleri, *İş Ahlakı Dergisi*, 2(4), 71-88.

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